

Enhancing Robust Autonomy of ROS 2 Systems: Code Generation and Monitoring for Deliberation Components

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Abstract—Hand-coded deliberation components for autonomous robots are prone to flaws. We present one tool which compiles models of deliberation components into executable code, and one which generates runtime monitors from the models, to reduce development effort and increase confidence in robot’s safety. Testing demonstrate the usefulness of combining model-based development, code generation, and monitoring.

I. INTRODUCTION

The *deliberation layer*, i.e., the components that shape the behavior of a robot considering its mission and the current state of the environment, is often critical in making autonomous decisions in dynamic and unstructured environments while maintaining safe and secure operations [1]. Increasing effort is being put in designing and implementing control architectures that guarantee the expected quality of service as well as stated safety and security requirements [2], [3]. To this end, we consider a model-based design (MBD) approach assuming that deliberation components are modeled at a conceptual level using abstractions such as finite-state machines (FSMs) and behavior trees (BTs), and that their implementations interact among them and with the other layers of the control architecture through well-defined protocols and a common middleware (ROS 2 in our case [4]).

We contribute two tools and their experimentation on a case study to show that we can ease the development of deliberation components and, at the same time, improve the confidence in their correct behavior without introducing unnecessary burden on the developers: Model2Code (M2C), which automatically compiles the models of deliberation components into executable code compatible with ROS 2; and MOnitoring-ON-line (MOON), which generates runtime monitors for *properties* and *models* to improve confidence in the generated code compliance with its specification. We test the combination of M2C and MOON in a simulated, but realistic, use-case scenario where we demonstrate that (i) M2C generates code that does not trigger unwanted or inefficient behaviors during execution, (ii) MOON can spot different faults injected in the implementation of deliberation components, and (iii) model monitors run without excessive overhead even in combination with property monitors generated from system requirements as described in [5]. Furthermore, we show that, in some cases, model monitors can spot issues that property monitors may not intercept.

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II. PRELIMINARIES

a) *CONVINCE project*: The tools and methods presented in this work are part of the CONVINCE project (CONtext-aware Verifiable and adaptIve dyNamiC dELiberation) which aims to develop a software toolchain that assists developers in designing and developing fully verified robot deliberation systems [3]. The CONVINCE architecture is composed of three layers: a **deliberation layer** which orchestrates the various skills; a **skill layer** which implements basic robot capabilities; and a **functional layer** which interacts directly with the hardware. These layers exchange data and coordinate with each other via a middleware.

b) *BTs*: BTs [6] are widely used in robotics for model-based design of deliberation policies [7], [8]. Our implementations are based on the semantics implemented by the library `BehaviorTree.cpp`¹.

c) *FSMs*: FSMs are commonly used to model policies and to represent either abstract or concrete models of the functional and control stages of a software architecture, hardware components or the environment. We represent state machines using a subset of the SCXML standard [9], enriched with ROS 2-specific elements such as “services” and “topics” for code generation and monitoring.

d) *Middleware*: In this paper we assume that BT and FSMs models are based on ROS 2 [4], a communication middleware widely used in the robotics community. ROS 2 is mainly composed of three primary interfaces: **topics** are based on the publisher-subscriber pattern, are asynchronous and typed; **services** are based on the client-server pattern, are synchronous and typed; and **actions** are a fusion between services and topics, made for long computations.

III. METODOLOGY

a) *Specification and code generation*: To bridge the gap between the skill layer (specified in SCXML) and the functional layer requires an interface that translates SCXML events into actionable commands that interact with the middleware. M2C² is a tool designed to automate the generation of this interface system for each state machine, whose manual development would be time-consuming and error-prone. M2C employs a template-based approach, taking as input the SCXML models and generating as output the corresponding ROS 2 C++ code that translates SCXML events into ROS 2 interfaces. The input files include the SCXML model and the XML file describing the system architecture

¹<https://www.behaviortree.dev/>

²<https://github.com/convince-project/model2code>

specifying the definition of the interfaces. Starting from a set of C++ template files, it produces the following output: C++ header and source of the executable skill, a main file containing the event handling code and the corresponding ROS 2 translation, the `CMakeLists.txt` configuration file and the XML ROS 2 package file. The output can be built directly with *CMake* without further editing.

b) Monitor generation and monitoring: MOON³ is a runtime monitor implemented on top of ROSmonitoring [10], that accepts the same model specification as M2C and provides monitor generation for properties and models. MOON relies on asynchronous communication facilities provided by the publish-subscribe mechanisms available in ROS 2 to inspect messages travelling across channels. For monitoring models, it introduces man-in-the-middle components that intercepts ROS 2 messages. In the case of property specifications, the oracle checks that the monitored communication channels satisfy a property [5]. In the case of model specifications, the oracle considers the FSM model of a skill and ensures that the execution of the skill implementation, generated by M2C from the very same FSM, is compliant with the model. The oracle is currently implemented using the Apache Commons SCXML library⁴ to support SCXML models. The model specification is compiled into a fully compliant SCXML state machine, called the Oracle State Machine, and used at runtime to evaluate if the skill is compliant to its FSM specification. The oracle processes inputs and outputs of the monitored skill and simulates its behavior by forwarding the monitored communication to the Oracle State Machine, and compares produced outputs with monitored ones, alerting in case any discrepancy is found. Since all relevant information is included in our model specification, MOON automatically generates the monitor configuration.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

a) Use case description: We consider a scenario in which a humanoid robot guides visitors on a laboratory tour. The robot navigates the laboratory to reach two predefined points of interest while actively ensuring that visitors are following, stopping when they fall behind. It also monitors its battery level, triggering an alarm when it drops below a certain threshold. The functional layer is not implemented by us and we only know about its interfaces, the skill layer is implemented with FSMs and the deliberation layer is implemented with a BT. All the communications happens through the ROS 2 middleware.

b) Monitoring: Each property is specified through a pattern [11] which is translated to a temporal logic formula from which a property monitor can be generated [5]. Model monitors are generated from the FSMs designed by developers, without additional effort placed on them. To evaluate the ability of the system to detect anomalous circumstances, bugs are injected into the selected skills, either on the SCXML

State Machine or in the generated code. We introduced three different categories of faults: **unresponsiveness** (the skill does not respond to the tick); **incorrect response** (the skill responds to the tick but not always correctly); and **incorrect parameter names** (the skill has a spelling error, for example in the event, service, or topic name). The code used for the experiments can be found on GitHub⁵.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

For the tests we use a single fault model, i.e., in each configuration a single bug is injected, ensuring that this is the only difference from the nominal behavior of the system.

a) Unresponsiveness: The skill does not respond to the tick, so the BT is stuck waiting for the response. Once executed, the model monitor detects right away a difference between the outputs of the skill and its specification, since the latter has an additional event, i.e., the tick response, and raises an anomaly after a timeout. The property monitor either does not detect any anomaly or it detects a violation of a related property much later in the execution.

b) Incorrect response: The skill response to the tick is aleatory due to errors in the state machines. The model monitor detects the anomaly at the first occurrence. In one case, the property monitor detects the fault at the same time as the model monitor, while in another case it never does.

c) Incorrect parameter name: The skill has a misspelling in the name of a parameter and calls an unmonitored interface, so the model monitor does not receive any information about the call to the functional layer. In one case, the property monitor detects the anomaly at the same time as the model monitor. In another case, the model monitor detects the anomaly immediately, while the property monitor does not detect any anomaly.

d) Overhead: Measuring the tick time of each skill with and without model monitors, we find that, due to using a synchronous man-in-the middle, model monitors add on average 100–150 millisecond of overhead per skill. Thus, while the overhead is non-negligible, monitoring properties and models together is feasible.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RELATED WORK

Our experimental results prove that automating the generation of skill implementations and monitoring the resulting code can effectively increase confidence in the correct behavior of deliberation components without increasing the burden of developers. Our tests also demonstrate that model monitors can successfully complement property monitors. To the best of our knowledge, the only framework that targets the same objectives as ours is presented in [12], [13]. While several approaches featuring MBD, off-line verification, and monitoring have been successfully applied to robotics [13], most of them do not provide code generation from conceptual models (as done by M2C) together with property and model monitoring (as provided by MOON), both on top of a widely used and supported middleware such as ROS 2.

³<https://github.com/convince-project/MOON>

⁴<https://github.com/apache/commons-scxml>

⁵<https://github.com/convince-project/CGM-IROS2025>

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